

LINGUISTICS AS SCIENCE ABOUT LANGUAGE

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Abstract. Linguistics studies languages as defined code system adopted is a particular group of people for communication. In linguistics defined two levels of language learning: the mastery of correct speech, language subordinate standards, and mastery of appropriate speech and communicative qualification. Currently, the practice is becoming increasingly common ability of the individual visual to communicate in two or more languages, which is becoming increasingly important in the life of society.

Key words: linguistics; language; linguistic basis of language learning; language teaching methodology as a science.

Linguistics is one of the most ancient sciences. Having separated from the animal world and having begun to recognize himself as a subject opposed to nature as an object of his practical and cognitive activity, man turned his attention to himself. The subject of his reflections became himself, namely his place in the universe, the secrets of his origin, his physical and mental properties, his ability to communicate with his own kind, language as the main means of such communication, various aspects of the linguistic phenomenon.

The term "linguistics" is derived from the French word *linguistique* (*lingua* - "language"). It is a science about language, studying its many aspects: text linguistics, applied linguistics, mathematical, descriptive.

Linguistics studies not only existing (existing or possible in the future) languages, but also human language in general. In the broad sense of the word, linguistics is divided into scientific, i.e., presupposing the construction of linguistic theories, and practical. Most often, scientific linguistics is implied by linguistics.

Theoretical linguistics studies the laws of language and formulates them as theories. It can be descriptive (describing real speech) and normative (indicating how one “should” speak and write).

Linguistics includes observation; recording and description of speech facts; putting forward hypotheses to explain these facts; formulating hypotheses in the form of theories and models describing language; their experimental verification and refutation; forecasting speech behavior. Explanation of facts can be internal (through linguistic facts) or external (through physiological, psychological, logical or social facts).

One of the most important concepts of modern linguistics is the concept of units of language: word, sentence, phrase, syllable, phoneme, etc.

Linguistics is divided into sections according to different aspects of its subject: grammar (studies and describes the structure of words and word inflection, types of phrases and types of sentences);

- graphics (investigates the relationships between letters and signs);
- lexicology (studies the vocabulary of a language, or lexicon);
- morphology (rules for constructing nominative units (word forms) from the simplest significative units (morphemes) and, conversely, dividing word forms into morphemes);
- onomastics (studies proper names, the history of their origin and transformation as a result of long-term use in the source language or in connection with borrowing from other languages of communication);
- orthography (spelling, a system of rules that determine the uniformity of methods of conveying speech in writing);
- pragmatics (studies the conditions under which speakers use linguistic signs);
- semantics (the semantic side of language);
- semiotics (studies the properties of sign systems);
- stylistics (studies the various expressive possibilities of language);
- phonetics (studies the features of speech sounds);
- phonology (studies the structure of the sound system of language and the functioning of sounds in the language system);
- phraseology (studies stable turns of speech); – etymology (studies the origin of words).

Therefore, linguistics is a science that studies language. It provides information about what distinguishes language from other phenomena of reality, what its elements and units are, how changes occur in language.

Linguistic foundations of language teaching

Language, considered as a means of communication, is a complex phenomenon in which various aspects can be distinguished.

Thus, F. de Saussure distinguished between linguistic activity, an integral part of which is language, i.e. a system of signs that combine meaning and acoustic image, and speech, which he considered an individual act of will and understanding.

L.V. Shcherba distinguished three aspects of language: speech, by which he understood the process of speaking and understanding; language, i.e. grammatical and lexical rules; linguistic material, i.e. the sum of individual acts of speaking and understanding, continuing in memory.

Thus, language has two sides: the language system, which includes both the grammar system and the sound structure and vocabulary of the language, and speech, expressed in speech units, i.e. activity, which, naturally, should include the result of this activity - various kinds of texts, from fragments carved on stones to printed volumes of books.

V.D. Arakin gives the following definition of speech: it is human activity, formalized in speech units (sentences), constructed according to the rules of grammar of a given language and expressing certain thoughts. The simplest unit of speech is a sentence expressing a complete judgment and consisting of words of a given language, changed according to the rules of morphology and connected according to the rules of syntax of a given language.

Modern linguistics understands language as a socially significant communicative code and the rules of its functioning, fixed in the consciousness of a particular group of people. In other words, language is a system of linguistic means necessary and sufficient for communication, and the rules for their use. Speech is the realization of the linguistic system in specific acts of communication, i.e. it includes both the communication process itself and speech products or products of this process. Taking such a distinction into account is very important for methodology.

The study of language in the strict sense of the word, as L.V. Shcherba has shown, provides only knowledge of the language system, but does not lead to the use of this system as a means of communication. For the practical use of language, i.e. for mastering speech, it is necessary not only to know the language means and the rules for their use in speech, but also to use them automatically in acts of

communication. It follows from this that in the process of learning it is necessary to provide not only for the memorization and consolidation of language means in memory, the formation of skills in using them, but also for practice in communication, i.e. in the implementation of speech acts.

Both the language system and speech are inseparable from each other and, in fact, one does not exist without the other. Thus, the language system outside of speechBoth the language system and speech are inseparable from each other and, in fact, one does not exist without the other. Thus, the language system outside of speech in a given language loses its essence, since it cannot serve as a means of communication. Speech outside of the language system, i.e., not following the rules existing in a given language, becomes incoherent and again ceases to serve the purposes of communication, i.e., loses its essence. All changes occur first in speech in the form of individual facts. These individual facts, contradicting the established language system, gradually increase in number and acquire an increasingly pronounced systemic character, while still remaining in speech. Finally, they break the existing language system and, modifying it, pass from speech to the language system.

Thus, speech and the language system are two sides of a complex unity. When mastering a language, one should move in the direction from speech to language.

Methodology of language teaching as a science

The methodology is interpreted as a theory of language teaching, which is a strictly structured system of knowledge about the patterns of “communication” of a learner to a new linguistic culture (language + culture) in connection with the native language and original culture of the learner.

As is known, methodology as a scientific discipline is connected with the educational environment created by a person and in which he is the main actor. It is the personality, which is in the dimension of at least two linguacultures, that is recognized in modern linguodidactics as a value, while such categories as personal experience, emotions, opinions, feelings acquire special significance. This gives grounds to link foreign language education not only with the “appropriation” by the student of a certain set of foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities, but also with the change of his motives, relationships, personal positions, system of values and meanings. This is the main goal of language education at the present stage of its development.

In relation to the essence of language education, this means that students in an educational situation must demonstrate their own activity in order to solve communicative and cognitive tasks of a creative and problematic nature.

Since, from the position of the anthropocentric paradigm, a person masters a language through the awareness of his theoretical and practical activity in it and with its help, new semantic components of methodological theories/concepts/approaches are put forward in modern methods: “language education is not for life, but through life!”, “to learn not the language, but with the help of the language”. This also has quite specific methodological “consequences”, postulated as new linguaeducational principles. For example, actualization of the cognitive, creative and research activities of the student; shifting the emphasis from teaching to activities related to language study/language acquisition; reducing the “simulation” of foreign language communication in favor of “authentic communication in the target language”; solving diverse problems with the help of language; activating the productive activity of students with an exit to the real socio-cultural context, etc.

Thus, methodological knowledge is the main object and result of cognition. At the same time, scientific knowledge, content and sequence of cognitive actions always occur in educational discourse at two levels: theoretical and empirical. At the theoretical level of methodological knowledge, the most important research methods are abstraction and idealization, which allow one to abstract from many factors that influence the real and very complex process of teaching and learning, and to formulate methodological concepts, substantiate concepts (models) of learning, as well as methodological approaches to learning.

In other words, the result of scientific research by methodologists are formulated theoretical postulates and theoretical constructs, which, as a rule, are tested in practice and confirmed by the practice of teaching. At the empirical level, where such methods as observation and experiment are used as analytical tools, the basis is created for the primary theoretical understanding of certain methodological phenomena, when certain ideas, data, and information that are of particular importance for the educational space are obtained in direct interaction with reality and taking into account the identified objective patterns.

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